

Terpenoids : Part III. A New Synthesis of dl-Calamenene

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Synthesis of dl-calamenene has been achieved. 1,6-Dimethyl-4-acetyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene, obtained through Diels Alder reaction of α -p-dimethyl styrene and methyl vinyl ketone, has been converted to 1,6-dimethyl-4(ethyl-1'-bromo)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene. The latter bromide, on submission to lithium-dimethyl copper in tetrahydrofuran, affords the terpenic hydrocarbon.

Sorm and coworkers¹ on the basis of physical and chemical studies, established the structure (I) for the naturally occurring sesquiterpene hydrocarbon calamenene, which they confirmed through a synthesis¹.

In the present studies, we have developed a new and facile route to calamenene. The diagram illustrates the sequence of reactions employed.

1. F. Sorm, K. Veres and V. Herout, *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, **18**, 106; *Chem. Abst.*, 1953, **47**, 8700.

α -*p*-Dimethyl styrene (II)² was subjected to Diel's Alder reaction with methyl vinyl ketone in the presence of catalytic amount of hydroquinone to afford 1,6-dimethyl-4-acetyl-1, 2, 3, 4 tetrahydronaphthalene (III) in 69.5% yield which was treated with sodium ethoxide to fix the acetyl group in the equatorial position. The ketone (IIIa) was chromatographed over alumina and characterised through its I.R. absorption spectrum. The ketone (IIIa) was submitted to the lithium aluminium hydride reduction when 1,6-dimethyl-4-(ethanol-1')-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV) was obtained in 79.0% yield. The carbinol (IV) was converted into its corresponding bromide, 1, 6-dimethyl-4(ethyl-1'-bromo)-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (V) with phosphorus tribromide in dry benzene in 61.5% yield.

The bromide (V) was subjected to lithium dimethyl copper reaction³ in tetrahydrofuran at 0° to afford 1, 6-dimethyl-4-isopropyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (I) which is purified through chromatography. This was further purified by distillation to yield calamenene (I) in 85.6% yield. This synthetic hydrocarbon was characterised by its I.R. spectrum which was found to be identical with that of naturally occurring calamenene*.

EXPERIMENTAL

M.Ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. Microanalysis by Mr. B. N. Anand, Micro Analyst, Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I. R. spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer Infrared-Spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film.

1, 6-Dimethyl-4-acetyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IIIa): A mixture of α -*p*-dimethyl styrene (6.5 g.), methyl vinyl ketone (7.0 g.) and hydroquinone (0.3 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at 180° for 6 hr. and at 200° for further 2 hr. The product was cooled and chromatographed on alumina, eluting with 10% benzene-pet. ether (b.p. 40-60°) mixture. This was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to obtain 1, 6-dimethyl-4-acetyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III), b.p. 140-45°/8 mm. It was warmed with sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.75 g. of sodium and 25 ml. of absolute ethanol), for 3 hr. After the usual work up, it gave (IIIa), b.p. 140-43°/10 mm.; yield 7.1 g. (69.5%). ³¹n_D 1.5440; I.R. spectrum⁴: 2950 cm⁻¹ (—C—CH₃); 1715 cm⁻¹ (—C = O); 3020, 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); 810 cm⁻¹ (toluene). (Found: C, 83.15; H, 8.91; C₁₄H₁₈O requires C, 83.12; H, 8.97%).

1, 6-Dimethyl-4-(ethanol-1')-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV): A fine suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.75 g.) in dry ether (150 ml.) was added the compound (III) (6.8 g.) in 50 ml. ether at such a rate so as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. When the addition was complete, the contents were stirred and refluxed for 1 hr. After cooling, water (5 ml) was added cautiously to destroy excess of lithium aluminium hydride. The reaction mixture was then decomposed by slow addition of ice-cold dilute sodium sulphate solution keeping the temperature below 5°, stirring being continued. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted thrice with ether. The combined ethereal extract was then

2. A. S. Onishchenko, *Diene Synthesis*, 1964, 495.

3. E. J. Corey and G. H. Posner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 3912.

* We are grateful to Prof. V. Herout for providing the I.R. spectrum of naturally occurring calamenene.

4. A. D. Cross, "Introduction to Practical I. R. spectroscopy", Butterworth's Scientific Pub., London (1960).

successively washed with water, 5% sodium carbonate solution, water and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removing the solvent, the residual oil was vac-distilled to afford (IV), 5.40 g. (79% yield), b.p. 150-55°/10 mm., $^{31}\eta_D$ 1.5435; I.R. spectrum; 3450 cm^{-1} (—OH); 2950 cm^{-1} (—C—CH₃); 3020, 1600 cm^{-1} (aromatic); 810 cm^{-1} (toluene). (Found : C, 82.26; H, 9.90. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 82.30; H, 9.87%).

1,6-Dimethyl-4(ethyl-1'-bromo) 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene(V) : A mixture of carbinol (IV) (5.2 g.), thiophene free benzene (30 ml.) and 1-2 drops of pyridine was chilled in ice-salt bath. To this was added phosphorus tribromide (3.2 g.) dropwise during 20 min. The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature during 6 hr. and kept at that temperature for 15 hr. Finally, it was heated to 60-65° for 1 hr. It was then cooled and poured slowly with stirring into ice-water. The decomposed product was allowed to stand for some time. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted four times with ether. The combined ether-benzene extract was washed free of acid with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was evaporated and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to give the bromide (V), (4.1 g) in 61.5% yield; b.p. 145-50°/8 mm., $^{31}\eta_D$ 1.5515; (Found : C, 62.95; H, 7.08; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}$ requires : C, 62.92; H, 7.12%).

1,6-Dimethyl-4-isopropyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene(I) : Methyl iodide (20.6 g) in dry T.H.F. (35 ml.) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of lithium (1.0 g.) in dry T.H.F. (200 ml.) kept under an atmosphere of nitrogen. After the complete dissolution cuprous iodide (13.5 g.) was added in small lots and stirred below 0° for about 1/2 hr. followed by the dropwise addition of (V) (3.8 g.) in T.H.F. (20 ml.), the contents being kept at the same temperature for further 6 hr. The slurry thus obtained was decomposed with ice-cold water, the product extracted with ether (5 × 100 ml.) and the combined extract washed thoroughly with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the residue chromatographed over alumina and eluted with petroleum ether (40-60°) to furnish 1, 6-dimethyl-4-isopropyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (I). The hydrocarbon was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure; b.p. 135-40°/15 mm., yield 2.45 g. (85.6%); $^{31}\eta_D$ 1.5415; I.R. spectrum; 3020, 1600 cm^{-1} (aromatic); 2950 cm^{-1} (—C—CH₃); 810 cm^{-1} (toluene) and other peaks at 1897, 1795, 1740, 1515, 1450, 1380, 1295, 1115, 1020, 965, 895, 790 and 740 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 89.12; H, 10.88; $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}$ requires C, 89.04; H, 10.96 %).

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